

SELF-CONFIDENCE AND SPEAKING FLUENCY AMONG ENGLISH 10 STUDENTS OF TUNASAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the correlation between self-confidence and English-speaking fluency among Grade 10 students at Tunasan National High School during the 2025–2026 academic year. The research employed a descriptive correlational approach and was grounded in Bandura’s Self-Efficacy Theory and Krashen’s Second Language Acquisition Theory. It aimed to examine how self-confidence, defined through motivation, positive mindset, self-awareness, and sense of purpose, related to students’ speaking fluency, which was measured across oral fluency, meaning and ideas, sentence structure, and vocabulary extent. A total of 30 respondents participated in the study. They completed a 40-item survey questionnaire that assessed their level of self-confidence in speaking English. Their speaking fluency was evaluated through a structured four-part oral assessment covering fluency, meaning and ideas, sentence construction, and vocabulary. The findings revealed that the respondents generally possessed very high self-confidence, with a mean of 3.25, and demonstrated a high level of speaking fluency, with a mean of 3.20. Statistical analysis indicated significant positive correlations between self-confidence and speaking fluency, with correlation coefficients ranging from $r = 0.136$ to 0.258 ($p < 0.05$). These results suggested that higher self-confidence was associated with greater oral proficiency in English. The study underscored the importance of fostering self-confidence alongside reinforcing grammatical knowledge and vocabulary development to enhance speaking fluency. It highlighted the need for educational interventions and structured programs that integrated affective support with language practice. These findings had practical implications for teachers, school administrators,

and curriculum designers seeking to improve English oral communication skills among Filipino secondary students.

Keywords: *Self-confidence, speaking fluency, English, descriptive correlational*

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized and competitive world, fluency in spoken English is no longer just an advantage but an essential skill. English remains the primary language of international communication in fields such as science, business, medicine, and education (Ali, 2022). As countries become more interconnected, the ability to communicate effectively in English allows individuals to participate in academic, professional, and cultural exchanges. Speaking fluency, defined by Lennon (as cited in Ghasemi et al., 2021) as the smooth and effortless use of language, includes clarity, coherence, and the natural flow of speech. Because of this, developing English speaking fluency has become increasingly important for learners worldwide.

One of the most significant factors affecting speaking fluency is self-confidence. Self-confidence enables learners to express themselves without excessive fear of making mistakes or being judged. Students who believe in their abilities are more likely to join discussions, participate in oral activities, and communicate actively. Moradiyousefabadi and Ghafournia (2023) found that learners with higher self-confidence often demonstrate better language proficiency, including stronger pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar. Similarly, Aulia and Apoko (2022) reported a significant relationship between self-confidence and speaking ability. On the other hand, learners with low confidence frequently experience anxiety, hesitation, and fear, which negatively affect their speaking performance (Namaziandost et al., 2024). These findings show that self-confidence is closely related to speaking fluency.

In the Philippines, English proficiency has greatly contributed to economic growth and global competitiveness. The country is known for industries such as Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) and English as a Second Language (ESL) teaching. Kodnani (2024) reported that the BPO sector generated \$30 billion in revenue and employed about 1.3 million Filipinos. Meanwhile, the ESL industry continues to attract international learners (Yeh, as cited in Santos et al., 2022). These developments emphasize the importance of maintaining strong English communication skills among Filipino learners and workforce.

However, recent reports suggest a decline in English proficiency among Filipino learners. The Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries in reading in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). In addition, the Functional Literacy, Education, and Mass Media Survey (FLEMMS) stated that nearly 18 million graduates may be functionally illiterate. These findings indicate serious concerns regarding literacy and communication skills. Since reading and speaking are interconnected, weak reading ability may also affect oral fluency.

At Tunasan National High School (TNHS), similar challenges have been observed among students, particularly in speaking English. Many learners struggle to express their ideas clearly and confidently. One possible reason is low reading proficiency. Based on the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) conducted in July 2025, 1,299 out of 5,052 students were classified as frustration readers (Castro, 2025). Students with limited reading skills often have weaker vocabulary and comprehension, which may hinder their ability to speak effectively. Supporting this, Bilge and Kalenderoglu (2022) and Khasanah and Safriyani (2021) found strong relationships among vocabulary knowledge, reading comprehension, and speaking ability.

Aside from language difficulties, many students also experience low self-confidence. Classroom observations show that some learners have ideas to share but hesitate to speak because they fear making grammatical mistakes, mispronouncing words, or being judged by classmates. Others avoid speaking activities entirely. This lack of participation slows the development of fluency, since speaking skills improve through regular practice and interaction. Thus, students' speaking difficulties may result not only from limited language knowledge but also from fear and low confidence.

Given the global importance of English communication and the challenges faced by students locally, it is necessary to examine the factors affecting speaking fluency. Self-confidence is an important factor because it influences learners' willingness to communicate, take risks, and engage in speaking tasks. Understanding its relationship with fluency can help teachers create effective strategies to support students.

This study aimed to determine the relationship between self-confidence and speaking fluency among Grade 10 students of Tunasan National High School. It also sought to provide localized evidence that may help improve English learning. The findings may serve as the basis for practical interventions, such as a modular kit or classroom activities designed to strengthen both self-confidence and speaking fluency. Ultimately, the study hopes to help students become more confident and effective English speakers prepared for future academic and professional opportunities.

Research Questions

The study evaluated the correlation of self-confidence and Speaking Fluency Among English 10 Students of Tunasan National High School. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following problems:

1. What is the self-confidence level of the English 10 students of Tunasan National High School in terms of:
 - 1.1 motivation,
 - 1.2 positive mindset,
 - 1.3 self-awareness, and
 - 1.4 self-purpose?
2. What is the speaking fluency level of the English 10 students of Tunasan National High School, as assessed by English teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 oral fluency,

- 2.2 meaning and ideas,
 - 2.3 sentence structure, and
 - 2.4 vocabulary extent?
3. Is there a significant relationship between self-confidence and speaking fluency levels of the English 10 students of Tunasan National High School?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what speaking fluency program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study followed a descriptive correlational approach. Barooah (2025) defined descriptive correlational quantitative research design as one employed to identify relationships between variables without manipulating them. Meanwhile, Devi et al. (2022) described correlational research as a non-experimental design used to examine the relationships between two or more variables within a single group. It identified the strength and direction of these relationships without manipulating or controlling the variables and does not establish cause-and-effect connections. The gathered data were statistically analyzed using appropriate inferential tools to determine the correlation between the students' level of self-confidence in speaking English and their level of speaking fluency.

This study administered a survey questionnaire and an interview-type instrument to gather data necessary for evaluating the respondent's English – self-confidence and speaking fluency. The self-confidence and the speaking fluency instrument were both based on existing research. The Self-Confidence in Speaking English instrument was adapted from the study of Risch (2021), consisting of 40 items in total, with 10 items for Motivation, 10 items for Positive Mindset, 10 items for Self-Awareness, and 10 items for Sense of Purpose. On the other hand, the speaking fluency instrument was adopted from the study of Failanga (as cited in Nonato and Pastolero, 2022) which was also based on an oral fluency assessment developed by Fresno Schools California, and consisted of four components were to be administered and scored through a one-on-one interview format, and with five levels- Level 1 to Level 5- of assessment for Oral Fluency, Meaning and Ideas, Sentence Structure, and Vocabulary Extent. The four (4) point scale ranged from four (4) being the highest to one (1) as the lowest for assessing the speaking fluency of the respondents. or acceptability, Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio/Content Validity Index (CVR/CVI) was computed, yielding an overall score of 1.0, which confirmed that the questionnaire was highly valid.

The validation process resulted in a Content Validity Index (CVI) of 1.00, reflecting complete agreement among evaluators on the appropriateness and relevance of the survey questionnaire in measuring the self-confidence and speaking fluency in English of the grade 10 learners.

Following expert validation, the instrument underwent reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha to assess its internal consistency. The results indicated satisfactory reliability across all subscales: Motivation $\alpha = .744$ (10 items) – Acceptable, Positive

Mindset $\alpha = .734$ (10 items) – Acceptable, Self-Awareness $\alpha = .849$ (10 items) – Good, and Sense of Purpose $\alpha = .765$ (10 items) – Good. These reliability coefficients confirmed that the instrument was internally consistent and appropriate for measuring the intended constructs.

After obtaining approval from Tunasan National High School, the self-confidence questionnaire and speaking fluency assessment were administered. Conducted from June to October 2025, the respondents of the study included 30 students from Grade 10 that represented Clusters 1 to 4.

The collected data was organized, analyzed, and interpreted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics, specifically the mean, were utilized to assess the level of self-confidence and level of speaking fluency in English of the Grade 10 students. Furthermore, the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r) was applied to determine the relationship between the variables, the gathered data were statistically analyzed using Pearson- r correlation to determine the relationship between students' self-confidence and English-speaking fluency.

This study centered on selected Grade 10 students of Tunasan National High School during the first quarter of the 2025–2026 academic year. It focused on correlating the self-confidence in speaking English of learners, particularly in its indicators of motivation, positive mindset, self-awareness, and sense of purpose, to their level of speaking fluency measured by their oral fluency, meaning and ideas, sentence structure, and vocabulary extent. The research applied descriptive correlational design over the first grading period of the academic year.

The limitations of this study were recognized. Firstly, the findings were specific to selected Grade 10 students of Tunasan National High School during the first quarter of the 2025–2026 academic year. They were not applicable to students at other grade levels, educational institutions, or educational circumstances. Secondly, the focus of the study was on the speaking skills and self-confidence in speaking English of the learners and did not extend to other subject areas and skills such as writing and reading. Lastly, this study was limited to the sample of students selected during the 2025–2026 academic year, which restricted the scope of the results to a broader student population.

The goal of this descriptive correlational study was to verify the correlation between the level of self-confidence in speaking English and the level of speaking fluency among English 10 learners in Tunasan National High School within the time period specified above. Conversely, it was important to remember that the findings of the study were applied only to its participants and should not have been interpreted as a gauge of the self-confidence and speaking skills in English of those who were not included in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the self-confidence level of the English 10 students of Tunasan National High School in terms of:

1.1 Motivation

Table 1.1 Self-Confidence Level of the English 10 Students of Tunasan National High School in terms of Motivation

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. I am good at English and I do not feel shy in speaking it in front of the class.	2.77	H	10
2. I am determined to improve my English-speaking skills because it will help me achieve my goals.	3.60	VH	1
3. I am passionate in English class because I love being challenged.	3.17	H	8
4. I stay motivated in English class because I know it prepares me for future academic and career opportunities.	3.43	VH	3
5. I feel proud when I am able to explain my ideas in English without hesitation.	3.27	VH	6
6. I feel motivated when I see improvement in my English-speaking performance.	3.40	VH	4
7. I feel more confident each time I speak English during class activities.	3.10	H	9
8. I enjoy challenging myself to reach new levels of fluency through independent practice.	3.37	VH	5
9. I enjoy speaking English because it allows me to connect with more people and express myself clearly.	3.20	H	7
10. I stay motivated and committed when working toward improving my English-speaking skills.	3.53	VH	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.28	VH	
STANDARD DEVIATION	0.687		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very High (VH) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ High (H) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Low (L) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Low (VL)

The self-confidence level of the English 10 students of Tunasan National High School in terms of motivation was Very High, with a general assessment of 3.28 and a standard deviation of 0.687. Furthermore, the indicator “I am determined to improve my English-speaking skills because it will help me achieve my goals” had the highest mean score of 3.60 (Very High). Meanwhile, the indicator “I am good at English, and I do not feel shy in speaking it in front of the class” had the lowest mean score of 2.77 (High).

The findings imply that the learners are highly motivated to develop their English-speaking fluency and recognize the significance of learning English in attaining their goals, while self-consciousness may pose a challenge to maintaining high motivation in achieving oral fluency. Moreover, the standard deviation indicates that the data points are clustered closely around the mean, suggesting consistency and predictability.

A study by Ghafar (2023) found that individuals with high self-confidence in their English language abilities tended to achieve greater success in learning and speaking a second language. Self-confidence was shown to foster motivation, persistence, and a greater willingness to address language-related challenges. It was also associated with

stronger pronunciation, richer vocabulary, and more accurate grammar, key components of effective English communication. Therefore, an elevated level of motivation to learn English would have a profoundly positive impact on the respondents' growth in oral fluency in the language.

1.2 Positive Mindset

Table 1.2 Self-Confidence Level of the English 10 Students of Tunasan National High School in terms of Positive Mindset

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. I am not afraid of committing mistakes in class sometimes.	2.53	H	9.5
2. I do not like cheating because I believe in my own abilities.	3.40	VH	3.5
3. I am not worried about my classmates laughing at me or reacting negatively when I speak English in class.	2.53	H	9.5
4. I feel optimistic about the results that I get in English-speaking tasks.	2.93	H	8
5. I have the ability to learn how to speak English fluently	3.13	H	7
6. I believe that making mistakes is part of learning and helps me grow as an English speaker.	3.60	VH	1
7. I stay true to my work because I value honesty and self-improvement.	3.53	VH	2
8. I focus on my progress rather than worrying about others' opinions.	3.27	VH	6
9. I trust in my potential to become fluent in English through effort and practice.	3.37	VH	5
10. I view challenges and low scores as opportunities to work harder and do better next time.	3.40	VH	3.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.17	H	
STANDARD DEVIATION	0.772		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very High (VH) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ High (H) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Low (L) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Low (VL)

The self-confidence level of the English 10 students of Tunasan National High School in terms of positive mindset was High, with a general assessment of 3.17 and a standard deviation of 0.772. Furthermore, the indicator “I believe that making mistakes is part of learning and helps me grow as an English speaker” had the highest mean score of 3.60 (Very High). Meanwhile, the indicators “I am not afraid of committing mistakes in class sometimes” and “I am not worried about my classmates laughing at me or reacting negatively when I speak English in class” had the lowest mean score of 2.53 (High).

1.3 Self-awareness

Table 1.3 Self-Confidence Level of the English 10 Students of Tunasan National High School in terms of Self-awareness

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. I know my own ability when it comes to speaking in English	3.27	VH	6.5
2. I do not feel shy about correcting myself when I make a mistake when speaking in English.	3.23	H	8
3. I am able to recognize and accept my mistakes when speaking in English.	3.40	VH	2.5
4. I accept advice and instruction from others in order to improve	3.53	VH	1
5. I like measuring my own abilities and learning things on my own when practicing my English-speaking skills	3.30	VH	5
6. I am open to receiving feedback to help me become a better English speaker	3.27	VH	6.5

7.	I take responsibility for my learning and continuously look for ways to improve my English-speaking skills	3.37	VH	4
8.	I am not shy in asking the teacher more about our lesson in English class.	2.97	H	9
9.	I can easily express what I mean to say when speaking in English.	2.90	H	10
10.	I am willing to explore different strategies to enhance my learning	3.40	VH	2.5

GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.26	VH
STANDARD DEVIATION	0.655	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very High (VH) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ High (H) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Low (L) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Low (VL)

The self-confidence level of the English 10 students of Tunasan National High School in terms of self-awareness was Very High, with a general assessment of 3.26 and a standard deviation of 0.655. Furthermore, the indicator “I accept advice and instruction from others in order to improve” had the highest mean score of 3.53 (Very High). Meanwhile, the indicator “I can easily express what I mean to say when speaking in English” had the lowest mean score of 2.90 (High).

The findings imply that the students possess a very high level of self-awareness regarding their perceptions of learning English and that this may contribute to higher overall self-confidence when speaking the language. The results also indicate that the learners are very open to accepting help and feedback from others, such as their teachers and peers, to improve, and that they are aware of the challenges they experience in verbally expressing themselves in English. Furthermore, the standard deviation indicates that the data points are clustered closely around the mean, illustrating consistency and predictability.

Similarly, Romero et al. (2023), in their study published in the *Journal of English as a Formal Language*, found that factors such as traumatic experiences, language anxiety, external influences, learners’ motivation and interest, self-awareness, academic performance, learning styles and strategies, as well as perceptions of the value of the English language, contributed to the respondents’ low English language proficiency. The study also revealed that some students had already become aware of their difficulties in speaking English as early as the elementary level. Yousefabadi and Ghafornia (2024) also states that self-confidence is strongly linked to learners’ motivation, perseverance, and readiness to take risks in the process of language learning, qualities that are strengthened through being able to assess one’s abilities and viewpoints towards language

1.4 Self-purpose

Table 1.4 Self-confidence Level of the English 10 Students of Tunasan National High School in terms of Self-purpose

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI	Rank
1. I like to try new things that will help me develop my English-speaking skills	3.53	VH	2
2. I am not easily distracted by the things around me when I am working towards my goals.	2.60	H	10
3. I am able to participate well in our speaking activities during English class.	3.20	H	
4. I will study harder when I get unsatisfactory results.	3.40	VH	5

5. I have determined my goals and I am focused on achieving them.	3.43	VH	4
6. I believe that practicing English every day helps me become more fluent and confident.	3.57	VH	1
7. I take initiative to learn new English words and use them in conversations.	3.30	VH	7
8. I take every speaking activity as a chance to learn and become better.	3.33	VH	6
9. I take every opportunity to participate in class discussions to improve my communication skills	3.20	H	8.5
10. I remain focused on my goals because I know that consistent effort leads to success.	3.47	VH	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.30	VH	
STANDARD DEVIATION	0.562		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very High (VH) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ High (H) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Low (L) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Low (VL)

The self-confidence level of the English 10 students of Tunasan National High School in terms of self-purpose was Very High, with a general assessment of 3.30 and a standard deviation of 0.562. Furthermore, the indicator “I believe that practicing English every day helps me become more fluent and confident” had the highest mean score of 3.57 (Very High). Meanwhile, the indicator “I am not easily distracted by the things around me when I am working towards my goals” had the lowest mean score of 2.60 (High).

The data illustrate that the respondents have a very high sense of purpose when it comes to developing their speaking fluency in English, and this goal-driven attitude continues to propel the learners towards attaining speaking fluency. The results also indicate that students value consistent practice and believe it is effective for developing their speaking skills, while being easily distracted by their surroundings proves to be a big challenge in attaining their goals. Moreover, the standard deviation shows that the data points cluster closely around the mean, displaying consistency and predictability.

The Self-Efficacy Theory by Albert Bandura, as cited by Waddington (2023), posited that self-efficacy is an individual’s belief in their capacity to regulate their own motivation, behavior, and social environment. This theory further stated that an individual attained goals by setting goals for oneself.

Research Question 2. What is the speaking fluency level of the English 10 students of Tunasan National High School as assessed by English teachers?

Table 2 *Speaking Fluency Level of the English 10 Students of Tunasan National High School in terms of Fluency Indicators*

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. Oral Fluency	3.10	H	3
2.			
3. Meaning and Ideas	3.43	VH	1
4. Sentence Structure	3.07	H	4
5. Vocabulary Extent	3.20	H	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.20	H	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very High (VH) 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ High (H) 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Low (L) 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Low (VL)

The speaking fluency level of the English 10 students of Tunasan National High School in terms of fluency indicators was High, with a general assessment of 3.20. Among the indicators, “Meaning and Ideas” had the highest computed mean score of 3.43 (Very High). Meanwhile, the indicator “Sentence Structure” had the lowest computed mean score of 3.07 (High).

The findings imply that while English 10 students demonstrate a high level of speaking fluency, their strengths are more pronounced in expressing meaning and ideas than in constructing grammatically accurate sentences. This suggests that students are confident in communicating their thoughts and engaging in discussions but still need support in refining their sentence structure for greater clarity and correctness.

Speaking fluency was defined by Ghasemi et al. (2021) as the ability to speak smoothly, confidently, and without unnecessary pauses or hesitations. Wang et al. (2024) stated that creative thinking and academic enthusiasm were factors that influenced linguistic originality, which in turn involved producing unique meanings and ideas. On the other hand, sentence structure in speaking fluency was also influenced by self-confidence, as Namaziandost (2024) found that making grammatical mistakes contributed to students’ anxiety. Ananda and Hastini (2023) also noted that fear of making mistakes and limited vocabulary and grammatical knowledge made fluency in sentence structure a challenging task for learners, a challenge that was affected by their level of self-confidence, and vice versa. The importance of developing speaking fluency was further emphasized by Akhter (2022), who noted that improved English communication skills enhanced social interactions and expanded future career opportunities. Consequently, the English-speaking fluency of Filipino students was closely linked to their future prospects and their ability to communicate effectively on a global scale.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant relationship between self-confidence and speaking fluency levels among English 10 students of Tunasan National High School?

Table 3 *Test of Significant Relationship between the Self-confidence Level and Speaking Fluency Level among English 10 Students of the Tunasan National High School*

Self-confidence Level	Speaking Fluency Level	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Motivation	Speaking Fluency	.136*	.043	Significant	Reject H ₀
Positive Mindset		.258*	.038	Significant	Reject H ₀
Self-awareness		.229*	.024	Significant	Reject H ₀
Self-purpose		.154*	.045	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

There was a significant relationship between self-confidence level and speaking fluency levels among English 10 students at Tunasan National High School. The correlation coefficients ranged from $r = .136$ to $r = .258$, interpreted as very low positive

to low positive correlations. The computed p-values ($p = .043, .038, .024, \text{ and } .045$) were all less than the significance level ($p < 0.05$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

This implies that self-confidence plays a meaningful role in shaping speaking performance, as motivation, positive mindset, self-awareness, and self-purpose all show significant relationships with speaking fluency. Effective strategies, therefore, include building students' self-confidence alongside improving their language skills. Teachers foster confidence by creating supportive and non-threatening classroom environments, encouraging participation, and providing positive reinforcement, while structured speaking activities and continuous practice strengthen both confidence and fluency. Overall, enhancing self-confidence is a valuable pathway to improving students' speaking abilities, but it must be addressed alongside other key factors in language learning.

Furthermore, Szyska et al. (2024) found that correlational analyses revealed a positive relationship of moderate effect size between linguistic self-confidence and L2 communication confidence, indicating that both types of confidence were associated with L2 speech fluency.

Similarly, Aulia and Apoko (2022) confirmed a significant relationship between speaking fluency and self-confidence, reporting a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.548$, which exceeded the critical value of 0.361 at a 5% significance level. Furthermore, the Affective Filter Hypothesis in Stephen Krashen's Second Language Acquisition Theory identified motivation, self-confidence, and anxiety as variables that influenced second language acquisition. Essentially, heightened emotions such as anxiety, fear, or embarrassment impeded language learning, as the affective filter functioned like an imaginary barrier in the mind that blocked input and obstructed cognitive processing. Conversely, when the affective filter was lowered, learners felt safe and comfortable, creating conditions that facilitated language acquisition.

Finally, Pham et al. (2021) found a significant relationship between self-confidence and performance, showing that students with higher self-confidence tended to perform better in presentation tasks. These students demonstrated stronger cognitive skills and were more capable of adjusting their learning strategies to develop comprehensive competence in English.

Research Question 4. Based on the findings of the study, what speaking fluency program may be proposed?

SPEAK-UP Kit: An Intervention toward Developing Self-Confidence in Speaking through Peer Dialogue in English as a Key to Upliftment and Progress

I. Program Description: The SPEAK UP Kit

Purpose:

1. Develop oral proficiency in English among Grade 10 students.

2. Utilize dialogic tasks to enhance students' ability to express themselves in English.
3. Measure progress through pre- and post-module analytic assessments.

Components of the SPEAK UP Kit:

1. Vocabulary Strengthening Kit (Module 1 – Vocabulary Made Easy):

- Easy definitions of the nine parts of speech (nouns, pronouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, conjunctions, prepositions, interjections, articles).
- Vocabulary lists for each part of speech.
- Simple sentence structures (SV, SVO, SVA, SVAdv, SVN).
- “Flex Your Learning” activity: students create sentences using different structures.

2. Sentence Completion Kit and Peer Dialogue Kit (Module 2 – Practice with Your Peers):

- Activity 1 – Meeting at the Mall: Guided role play using “Doing Kit” and “Reading Kit” with scripts and expression guides.
- Activity 2 – Chat and Choose: Conversation prompts using Instruction Cards and a Paper Fortune Teller for peer dialogue.
- Activity 3 – Guess My Goods: Picture cards; students describe objects while peers guess the item.
- Activity 4 – Never Have I Ever: Students respond to action cards by describing personal experiences.
- Activity 5 – Who Will I Be?: Students describe their dream job while peers guess, then reveal the answer.

3. Chatterbox Conversation Topic Selection:

- Encourages spontaneous conversation and peer interaction using engaging prompts.

General Instructions for Use:

1. Students are grouped in sizes of 3–10, based on class size and teacher discretion (recommended: free choice).
2. Begin with Module 1 to refresh basic English grammar knowledge.
3. After Module 1, groups select Module 2 activities based on interest.
4. Students may refer back to Module 1 during activities for reference.
5. Goal: Facilitate authentic, engaging peer conversations; focus on participation and engagement rather than scores or perfection.

Implementation Strategies:

1. Peer collaboration. – learners will perform speaking-fluency classroom-based activities.
2. Field-based tutoring. - English teachers will assist learners throughout their usage of the module.
3. Self-reflection. - Learners will use journals to monitor and process their learning journey towards speaking fluently.
4. Structured scaffolding to develop instructional and oral skills

Conclusions

The learners are highly motivated to develop their English-speaking fluency and recognize the importance of learning English in achieving their goals, although self-consciousness may hinder sustained motivation. The low standard deviation indicates consistency in responses. Respondents also demonstrate a positive mindset, viewing mistakes as opportunities for improvement, though fear of making mistakes in class remains a challenge. Students show a very high level of self-awareness, being open to feedback and recognizing their speaking difficulties, which may strengthen self-confidence. Likewise, they possess a very high sense of purpose, valuing consistent practice, although distractions in their surroundings may hinder progress.

That while English 10 students demonstrate a high level of speaking fluency, their strengths are more pronounced in expressing meaning and ideas than in constructing grammatically accurate sentences. This suggests that students are confident in communicating their thoughts and engaging in discussions but still need support in refining their sentence structure for greater clarity and correctness.

That self-confidence plays a meaningful role in shaping speaking performance of the students as to motivation, positive mindset, self-awareness, and self-purpose. Effective strategies are used including building students' self-confidence alongside improving their language skills. English teachers foster confidence by creating supportive and non-threatening classroom environments, encouraging participation, and providing positive reinforcement, while structured speaking activities and continuous practice strengthen both confidence and fluency.

The SPEAK-UP Kit was vital in strengthening both self-confidence and speaking fluency among Grade 10 students. The program can enhance students' self-confidence, lessen their fear of mistakes, and provide opportunities for oral practice hindered students' ability to communicate effectively in English.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. English teachers may implement engagement activities through pair and group conversational games and tasks, while also setting an encouraging and empathic classroom atmosphere to reduce the anxiety learners feel when speaking English before an audience.

2. English teachers and parents may cultivate a growth mindset approach by limiting risks and negative consequences when learners commit mistakes in speaking, and by sharing encouraging anecdotes and experiences. These practices may establish a positive mindset toward practicing English both in the classroom and at home.

3. Educators and school administrators may implement continuous evaluation and individualized feedback through regular formative assessments that identify students' strengths and areas for improvement. Analytic rubrics aligned with genre expectations may guide this feedback, encouraging students to revise their work accordingly and promoting confidence in their writing skills.

4. Educators may utilize the speaking fluency program proposed in this study to support self-confidence development and speaking fluency attainment in English. Involving students in group writing and peer feedback may allow them to negotiate meaning, share diverse viewpoints, and deepen their understanding of genre conventions, thereby enhancing social and communication skills.

5. Future researchers may build on the study's findings, conclusions, and recommendations by conducting similar investigations or exploring a broader range of purpose-driven leadership and school-based management practices. Longitudinal studies may be used to examine the sustained impact of interventions on self-confidence and speaking fluency among elementary and high school learners, offering insights that may inform curriculum transformation, pedagogical refinement, and educational policy.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical principles were carefully upheld throughout the conduct of the study. In accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, (Republic Act No. 10173), which safeguards the privacy of the personal data of all the respondents of the study. Data including personal information and the pretest and posttest results were stored securely under anonymity of the identity of the participants, where it was accessible only to the researcher and not revealed nor given to be used by any other individual or institution. All collected information was used strictly only for this study and in strict compliance with the ethical research guidelines of LCBA. The study made use of AI-assisted applications including ChatGPT for synthesis of ideas and Turnitin for checking for plagiarism. Nevertheless, all analyses, interpretations, and conclusions were original thoughts and ideas written by the researcher. AI was not used to generate research content nor to take the place of critical thinking. Ethical considerations in data privacy and academic integrity were followed and upheld to utmost consideration along with compliance with guidelines set by the educational institutions involved.

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